

Approaches to Learning and Academic Performance among Undergraduate Students in Organic Chemistry

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Abstract

The relationship between students' learning approaches and academic performance is a critical factor in higher education. This study examined the association between learning approaches and academic achievement among undergraduate students enrolled in an organic chemistry course. A cross-sectional survey design was employed, involving a purposive sample of 36 Level 200 undergraduate chemistry students (28 males, 8 females). Data were collected using the Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F). Pearson's correlation analysis revealed a weak, negative, and non-significant relationship between deep learning approaches and academic performance ($r = -0.132$), as well as between surface approaches and performance ($r = -0.273$). These findings suggest that neither deep nor surface learning approaches significantly predict academic outcomes in organic chemistry. The study highlights the need for pedagogical practices that promote reflective learning, intrinsic motivation, and deep engagement with course content.

Keywords: *approaches to learning, undergraduate students, organic chemistry, academic performance.*

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Introduction

The approach to learning reflects a learner's motivation, attitude, and mindset toward the learning process, and it may vary depending on the task or purpose at hand (Bartlett & Burton, 2007). Learning approaches capture students' intentions and attitudes toward their activities and processes (Biggs, 2001; Entwistle et al., 2006, as cited in Parpala et al., 2022). These perceptions strongly influence learning outcomes, as learners' attitudes toward tasks determine their level of engagement and effectiveness.

Marton and Säljö (1984) identified two primary learning approaches: surface learning, which emphasizes memorization, and deep learning, which focuses on comprehension and the meaningful acquisition of knowledge (Altıntaş & Görgeç, 2018). A deep approach involves becoming an autonomous learner capable of constructing

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knowledge, emphasizing meaningful understanding and connections (Wingate, 2007). In contrast, surface learning centers on fulfilling course requirements with minimal effort, often through rote memorization, without striving for deeper understanding (Biggs & Tang, 2007; Donnison & Penn-Edwards, 2012). Surface learners typically view content as isolated facts or procedures, engage without reflection, and experience anxiety due to low involvement, which often results in poor understanding and weak academic performance (Entwistle & Peterson, 2004; Donnison & Penn-Edwards, 2012).

In addition to surface and deep approaches, a strategic approach emphasizes how students organize their studies and manage time to achieve high grades (Entwistle & McCune, 2004; Parpala et al., 2022). Strategic learners aim to optimize their study efforts and strategies to excel academically, balancing efficiency with achievement. This approach is driven by a desire to succeed in assessments, but it also enhances self-esteem and motivation through academic accomplishment (Donnison & Penn-Edwards, 2012).

While surface learning leads to fragmented and superficial knowledge, deep learning supports personal growth by shifting students' perceptions, learning habits, and epistemological beliefs. It fosters meaningful engagement with subject matter, emphasizing core themes, principles, and ideas, while enabling the transfer and application of knowledge in varied contexts (Biggs & Tang, 2007).

Overall, approaches to learning play a critical role in shaping the quality of learning outcomes. Deep and strategic approaches are consistently associated with higher achievement, while surface approaches are negatively correlated with academic success (Altıntaş & Görden, 2018; Bälter et al., 2013).

Statement of the Problem

Students' approaches to studying play a significant role in shaping their academic outcomes (Bansal, Bansal, & White, 2021; Englund et al., 2022). Research suggests that these approaches are strongly influenced by the learning environment (Englund et al., 2022). For educators to enhance learning, it is essential to understand how students engage with their studies (Byrne et al., 2002; Byrne & Willis, 2008). Several factors, including the learning environment, program of study, and perceptions of academic quality, contribute to the approaches students adopt (Faranda et al., 2021). However, the evidence linking learning preferences directly to academic success remains inconclusive (Bansal, Bansal, & White, 2021). In addition, the relationship between learning approaches and performance is complex, since students may shift strategies depending on context and environment (Bunce & Bennett, 2021).

It is important to note that learning approaches are not fixed traits but are shaped by students' perceptions and the contexts in which they learn (Chiesi et al., 2016). Entwistle and Peterson (2004) emphasize that approaches evolve and can vary across different learning environments. This highlights the importance of examining approaches within specific academic contexts, such as organic chemistry. Since students' approaches directly affect their outcomes, investigating how these approaches relate to achievement in organic chemistry is essential (Parpala et al., 2022). The present study, therefore, seeks to explore the relationship between learning approaches and the academic performance of undergraduate students in organic chemistry.

Research Question

Is there a significant relationship between undergraduate students' approaches to learning and their performance in organic chemistry?

Literature Review

Approach to learning is a fundamental concept for understanding the processes that shape students' learning experiences (Lahdenperä et al., 2021). Marton and Säljö (1976, 1984) identified two qualitatively distinct approaches: deep learning and surface learning (Mørk et al., 2022). These approaches capture variations in students' intentions, motivations, and cognitive strategies during the learning process (Bunce & Bennett, 2021). Within this framework, learning is viewed as a combination of motives and strategies, categorized into deep (meaningful learning) and surface (rote learning) approaches (Ning & Downing, 2010).

A deep approach is characterized by efforts to understand, synthesize, and form a comprehensive view of the content. Deep learners critically engage with material, make connections, and derive meaning, often relating new knowledge to prior experiences or broader contexts (Lahdenperä et al., 2021; Marton & Säljö, 2005). They are typically intrinsically motivated, find enjoyment in learning, and apply their knowledge beyond academic settings (Biggs, 2003; Nordin et al., 2013).

In contrast, a surface approach emphasizes memorization and reproduction, often driven by the desire to avoid failure (Lahdenperä et al., 2021). Surface learners rely on repetitive techniques such as rote memorization, focusing on recalling information rather than understanding it. Their motivation is often extrinsic, to meet course requirements or perform adequately in assessments rather than engaging meaningfully with the material (Nordin et al., 2013).

Building on this framework, Entwistle (1979) introduced a strategic approach, where students aim to maximize academic performance by organizing time and effort efficiently and adapting to assessment demands. Strategic learners demonstrate strong organizational skills, effective study habits, and heightened awareness of assessment requirements. They often use past examination papers, optimize study conditions, and plan systematically to achieve the highest possible grades (Nordin et al., 2013; Bunce & Bennett, 2021).

Together, these approaches highlight the diverse ways students engage with learning, ranging from minimal effort and rote reproduction to intrinsic interest and meaningful understanding, with some students strategically balancing efficiency and performance.

Research consistently shows that students' approaches to learning strongly influence academic performance. High-achieving students typically adopt deep and strategic approaches, while low-achieving students rely more on surface approaches (Bansal et al., 2021). The surface approach is negatively correlated with grades, whereas the deep approach is positively associated with higher academic outcomes (Öhrstedt & Lindfors, 2019; Rowe, 2002).

These patterns hold across disciplines, with evidence that student characteristics, such as age, and the learning environment also shape learning approaches (Baeten et al., 2010; Biggs & Tang, 2011; Beccaria et al., 2014; Douglas et al., 2020; Rubin et al., 2018; Salamonson et al., 2013). For example, older students are more likely to adopt a deep approach, and higher-level conceptions of learning tend to align with deep strategies,

whereas lower-level conceptions correspond with surface strategies (Umapathy et al., 2020). Collectively, these findings underscore that adopting deep or strategic approaches is associated with more favorable academic outcomes, while surface approaches are linked to weaker performance.

Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative research approach with a cross-sectional survey design. A cross-sectional design was deemed appropriate because the objective was to examine the relationship between undergraduate students' approaches to learning and their academic performance in organic chemistry at a single point in time. Cross-sectional surveys provide a "snapshot" of a population, allowing researchers to describe existing conditions and explore relationships without manipulating variables or tracking changes over time (Hall, 2008). This design was therefore justified as suitable for efficiently collecting data from the target population within one academic semester.

The study sample consisted of 36 Level 200 undergraduate chemistry students enrolled in an organic chemistry course, comprising 28 males and 8 females. A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants. This method was considered appropriate because it allowed the researcher to specifically target students who were directly engaged in the organic chemistry course under investigation, ensuring that the data collected were relevant to the research objectives.

Data were collected using the Revised Two-Factor Study Process Questionnaire (R-SPQ-2F) developed by Biggs et al. (2001). The instrument is grounded in the theory of students' approaches to learning and measures two dimensions: deep approach and surface approach. It consists of 20 items, divided equally between the two subscales. Each subscale includes five items assessing students' motives for learning and five items assessing their strategies for learning.

Responses were rated on a five-point Likert scale, where each point indicates the degree to which a statement reflects the student's typical learning behavior: (1) Never or only rarely true of me – the statement does not reflect the student's behavior or motivation. (2) Seldom true of me – the statement applies occasionally but inconsistently. (3) Sometimes true of me – the statement is moderately applicable and occurs under certain conditions. (4) Often true of me – the statement frequently reflects the student's behavior or motivation. (5) Always or almost always true of me – the statement consistently reflects the student's approach to learning.

Scores were computed according to the procedure outlined by Biggs et al. (2001). The deep approach score was obtained by summing the deep motive and deep strategy items, while the surface approach score was calculated by summing the surface motive and surface strategy items. Students completed the R-SPQ-2F after participating in the organic chemistry course. Academic performance was assessed using their end-of-semester examination scores in organic chemistry.

Results and Discussion

Relationship Between Approaches to Learning and Academic Performance

Table 1 presents the Pearson correlation coefficients between students' approaches to learning and their performance in organic chemistry. The findings reveal weak,

negative, and non-significant correlations between both deep and surface approaches and exam performance, suggesting that learning approaches did not significantly predict achievement in this context.

Table 1. Pearson Correlation Between Approaches to Learning and Performance in Organic Chemistry

Variable	1	2	3
1. Exam score	—		
2. Deep approach	-0.13*	—	
3. Surface approach	-0.27*	0.07*	—

Note: N = 36. *p > .05 (not significant).

Figure 1 displays the scatter plot between the deep approach to learning and performance in organic chemistry, illustrating the weak, non-significant negative trend between the two variables. Similarly, Figure 2 presents the scatter plot between the surface approach and performance, which also shows a weak, non-significant negative relationship. Together, these visual representations reinforce the statistical findings that neither approach strongly influenced students' academic performance in organic chemistry.

Figure 1. Scatter Plot Showing the Relationship between the Deep Approach to Learning and Students' Performance in Organic Chemistry

Figure 2. Scatter Plot Showing the Relationship between the Surface Approach to Learning and Students' Performance in Organic Chemistry

Research findings on the relationship between learning approaches and academic performance have been mixed. Kember et al. (2008) found no significant correlation between deep and surface approaches, whereas Snelgrove and Slater (2003) reported that the deep approach was positively associated with performance and the surface motive negatively associated with it. Similarly, Öhrstedt and Lindfors (2019) observed that students with low surface and high strategic approaches tended to achieve higher grades, and Rowe (2002) also reported a moderate negative correlation between the surface approach and end-of-year grades. In contrast, Leung et al. (2008) found that surface approach scores remained consistently higher across all academic levels, suggesting relative stability in learning approaches over time. Other studies have indicated that deep and strategic approaches are generally linked to improved performance, although the strength of these associations is sometimes weak (Nordin, Wahab, & Dahlan, 2013). Furthermore, Bustamante et al. (2017) highlighted the predictive power of learning approaches, showing that they significantly influenced improvements in science readiness across the school year. Collectively, these studies reinforce the idea that deep and strategic approaches tend to support better academic outcomes, while surface approaches are often detrimental.

Conclusion

The results of this study revealed a weak, negative, and non-significant correlation between approaches to learning and performance in organic chemistry. This suggests that while learning approaches may influence academic performance, the relationship in this context was not strong enough to reach statistical significance. Nonetheless, the findings highlight the importance of fostering deep approaches to learning, as these are generally associated with more meaningful engagement and improved outcomes. Educational institutions can support this by implementing well-structured teaching and assessment methods that promote critical thinking and deeper understanding (McLoone & Oluwadun, 2012).

Reflective learning represents one strategy that can enhance both understanding and performance. By encouraging students to critically analyze their experiences, view them from multiple perspectives, and document their reflections, reflective learning fosters deeper comprehension. This approach has been successfully applied in the life sciences to improve student knowledge, teamwork, and analytical skills (Mayne, 2012). Byrne et al. (2002) further emphasize the need for educators to explicitly discuss different approaches to learning and link them to course requirements, including assessments. Providing timely feedback is also crucial, as it can guide students toward more effective strategies while discouraging reliance on surface approaches.

Since approaches to learning are strongly shaped by the teaching and learning environment, careful pedagogical design is essential. In particular, assessment for learning should account for students' learning approaches and their perceptions of assessment demands. Teachers play a vital role in fostering deep learning by stimulating intrinsic motivation and sustained interest in the subject matter. As Nordin, Wahab, and Dahlan (2013) note, this can be achieved by creating engaging learning environments, cultivating students' commitment to learning, and designing assessments that go beyond grade-oriented outcomes to promote practical skills, critical thinking, and meaningful application of knowledge.

References

- Altıntaş, S., & Görden, I. (2018). The effects of pre-service teachers' cognitive styles on learning approaches. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 7(4), 285–292. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v7i4.15737>
- Baeten, M., Kyndt, E., Struyven, K., & Dochy, F. (2010). Using student-centred learning environments to stimulate deep approaches to learning: Factors encouraging or discouraging their effectiveness. *Educational Research Review*, 5(3), 243–260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2010.06.001>
- Bälter, O., Cleveland-Innes, M., Pettersson, K., Scheja, M., & Svedin, M. (2013). Student approaches to learning in relation to online course completion. *Canadian Journal of Higher Education*, 43(3), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.47678/cjhe.v43i3.184673>
- Bansal, S., Bansal, M., & White, S. (2021). Association between learning approaches and medical student academic progression during preclinical training. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, 12, 1343–1351. <https://doi.org/10.2147/AMEP.S3292044>
- Bartlett, S., & Burton, D. (2007). Introduction to education studies. Sage.
- Biggs, J. (2003). Teaching for quality learning at university. Open University Press.
- Biggs, J., Kember, D., & Leung, D. Y. P. (2001). The revised two-factor Study Process Questionnaire: R-SPQ-2F. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 71(1), 133–149. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709901158433>
- Biggs, J., & Tang, C. (2007). *Teaching for quality learning at university: What the student does*. Open University Press.
- Bunce, L., & Bennett, M. (2021). A degree of studying? Approaches to learning and academic performance among student “consumers.” *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 22(3), 203–214. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14697874198602044>
- Bustamante, A. S., White, L. J., & Greenfield, D. B. (2017). Approaches to learning and school readiness in Head Start: Applications to preschool science. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 56, 112–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2016.10.012>
- Byrne, M., Flood, B., & Willis, P. (2002). The relationship between learning approaches and learning outcomes: A study of Irish accounting students. *Accounting Education*, 11(1), 27–42. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09639280210153254>
- Chiesi, F., Primi, C., Bilgin, A. A., Lopez, M. V., Fabrizio, M. del C., Gozlu, S., & Tuan, N. M. (2016). Measuring university students' approaches to learning statistics: An invariance study. *Journal of Psychoeducational Assessment*, 34(3), 256–268. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07342829155961255>
- Donnison, S., & Penn-Edwards, S. (2012). Focusing on first-year assessment: Surface or deep approaches to learning? *The International Journal of the First Year in Higher Education*, 3(2), 9–20. <https://doi.org/10.5204/intjfyhe.v3i2.1277>
- Englund, H., Stockhult, H., Du Rietz, S., Nilsson, A., & Wennblom, G. (2022). Learning-environment uncertainty and students' approaches to learning: A self-determination theory perspective. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2022.20427344>

- Entwistle, N. J. (1979). Stages, levels, styles or strategies: Dilemmas in the description of thinking. *Educational Review*, 31(2), 123–132. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0013191790310207>
- Entwistle, N. J., & McCune, V. (2004). The conceptual bases of study strategy inventories. *Educational Psychology Review*, 16(4), 325–345. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-004-0003-0>
- Entwistle, N. J., & Peterson, E. R. (2004). Conceptions of learning and knowledge in higher education: Relationships with study behaviour and influences of learning environments. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 41(6), 407–428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2005.08.009>
- Entwistle, N., McCune, V., & Tait, H. (2006). *ASSIST: Approaches and Study Skills Inventory for Students*. University of Edinburgh.
- Faranda, W. T., Clarke, T. B., & Clarke, I. (2021). Marketing student perceptions of academic program quality and relationships to surface, deep, and strategic learning approaches. *Journal of Marketing Education*, 43(1), 9–24. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02734753209392611>
- Hall, J. (2008). Cross-sectional survey design. In P. J. Lavrakas (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of survey research methods* (Vol. 1, pp. 173–174). Sage. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412963947>
- Kember, D., Leung, D. Y. P., & McNaught, C. (2008). A workshop activity to demonstrate that approaches to learning are influenced by the teaching and learning environment. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 9(1), 43–56. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1469787407086745>
- Lahdenperä, J., Rämö, J., & Postareff, L. (2021). Contrasting undergraduate mathematics students' approaches to learning and their interactions within two student-centred learning environments. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2021.19629988>
- Leung, D. Y. P., Ginns, P., & Kember, D. (2008). Examining the cultural specificity of approaches to learning in universities in Hong Kong and Sydney. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 39(3), 251–266. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022107313905>
- Lindblom-Ylänne, S., Parpala, A., & Postareff, L. (2019). What constitutes the surface approach to learning in the light of new empirical evidence? *Studies in Higher Education*, 44(12), 2183–2195. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2018.1482267>
- Marton, F., & Säljö, R. (1976). On qualitative differences in learning: II. Outcome as a function of the learner's conception of the task. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 46(2), 115–127. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8279.1976.tb02304.x>
- Marton, F., & Säljö, R. (1984). Approaches to learning. In F. Marton, D. J. Hounsell, & N. J. Entwistle (Eds.), *The experience of learning* (pp. 36–55). Scottish Academic Press.
- Marton, F., & Säljö, R. (2005). Approaches to learning. In F. Marton, D. Hounsell, & N. Entwistle (Eds.), *The experience of learning: Implications for teaching and studying in higher education* (3rd ed., pp. 39–58). University of Edinburgh, Centre for Teaching, Learning and Assessment.

- Mcloone, P., & Oluwadun, A. (2012). *Deep approaches to learning in higher education*. In SpringerReference (pp. 110–115). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/springerreference_302085
- Mørk, G., Gramstad, A., Åsli, L. A., Stigen, L., Johnson, S. G., Magne, T. A., Carstensen, T., Småstuen, M. C., & Bonsaksen, T. (2022). Approaches to studying: Changes during a three-year undergraduate study program. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2022.21482744>
- Ning, H. K., & Downing, K. (2010). Connections between learning experience, study behaviour and academic performance: A longitudinal study. *Educational Research*, 52(4), 457–468. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131881.2010.5247544>
- Nordin, N., Wahab, R. A., & Dahlan, N. A. (2013). Approaches to learning among trainee teachers: Malaysian experiences. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 105, 284–293. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.11.030>
- Öhrstedt, M., & Lindfors, P. (2019). First-semester students' capacity to predict academic achievement as related to approaches to learning. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 43(10), 1420–1432. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2018.14909500>
- Parpala, A., Mattsson, M., Herrmann, K. J., Bager-Elsborg, A., & Hailikari, T. (2022). Detecting the variability in student learning in different disciplines—A person-oriented approach. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 66(6), 1020–1037. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2021.19582566>
- Rowe, J. W. K. (2002). First-year engineering students' approaches to study. *International Journal of Electrical Engineering Education*, 39(3), 201–209. <https://doi.org/10.7227/IJEEE.39.3.33>
- Snelgrove, S., & Slater, J. (2003). Approaches to learning: Psychometric testing of a study process questionnaire. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 43(5), 496–505. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2648.2003.02747.x>
- Umapathy, K., Ritzhaupt, A. D., & Xu, Z. (2020). College students' conceptions of and approaches to learning computer science. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 58(3), 662–686. <https://doi.org/10.1177/07356331198726599>
- Wingate, U. (2007). A framework for transition: Supporting learning to learn in higher education. *Higher Education Quarterly*, 61(3), 391–405. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2273.2007.00361.x>

